

Concept-Based Text Classification Using Normalized Concepts Descriptors Weighting Method.

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ABSTRACT

This study proposes a Concept-Based Text Classification (CTC) framework using a Normalized Concept Descriptors Weighting Method (NCDWM) to enhance the accuracy and performance of text document classification. Existing CTC methods, such as the Ontology-Enabled Concept-Based Text Categorization (OCTC), have effectively reduced problems of synonymy and ambiguity but struggle with redundant descriptors that weaken discriminative power. To address this, the proposed method introduces an Inverse Concept Frequency (ICF) factor to penalize redundant descriptors while preserving their semantic significance. A dataset comprising abstracts from 100 articles in the ACM Digital Library, covering four major information science concepts, was used for experimentation. Results demonstrate that the proposed method improves classification accuracy from 62.5% (existing scheme) to 75%, while also increasing precision, recall, and F1-scores by 31%, 13%, and 21% respectively. These findings indicate that NCDWM strengthens semantic representation, enhances classification accuracy, and provides a more reliable approach for information retrieval systems.

Keywords: Concept-Based Text Classification, Redundant Descriptors, Inverse Concept Frequency, Semantic Representation, Information Retrieval.

1. INTRODUCTION

Information Retrieval (IR) is a central technique in natural language processing (NLP) that focuses on locating unstructured material, usually textual documents, from large collections to satisfy a specific information need (Manning, Raghavan, & Schütze, 2008). Essentially, it is a formal method of predicting the degree of relevance between a document and a user query. Although most Information Retrieval Systems (IRS) are designed and optimized for the English language, different languages possess unique features that can be accommodated with enhancements to IR techniques (Baeza-Yates & Ribeiro-Neto, 2011). One of the main challenges IRS addresses is the difficulty of extracting meaningful information from vast, unstructured datasets. While IRS provides useful solutions, its results are not always optimal, which has led to the integration of additional techniques, such as automatic text categorization, to enhance retrieval outcomes.

Automatic text categorization involves assigning documents to predefined categories using computer algorithms and has become increasingly important with the exponential growth of electronic text (Sebastiani, 2002). This method enables efficient organization, retrieval, and access to digital resources.

Typically, classification can be based on attributes such as author, type, or subject. Traditional approaches rely on assigning labels to documents, but this is insufficient when users lack prior knowledge of the labels. Consequently, research has focused on more sophisticated methods. For example, Lakshmi and Baskar (2019) introduced TF-RTF and TF-RFST term weighting schemes to improve document representation; however, their approach relied solely on statistical information and failed to capture semantic relationships such as synonymy. Similarly, Dogan and Uysal (2020) proposed TF-MONO, a novel term weighting strategy that enhances term discriminative ability, though it remains constrained by lexical-level analysis and suffers from ambiguity issues. More recently, Lee et al. (2021) presented the Ontology-enabled Concept-based Text Categorization (OCTC) method, which effectively reduces lexical mismatches and ambiguity but does not adequately handle redundant descriptors across multiple concepts.

1.1 Semantic and Feature-Based Approaches to Improving Text Document Classification

Several studies have attempted to improve the effectiveness of text document classification by addressing limitations such as synonymy, ambiguity, and inadequate feature representation. For instance, Deisy et al. (2010) introduced the Modified Inverse Document Frequency (MIDF) to reduce synonym issues by grouping related terms into word categories, though this approach failed to address word ambiguity. Similarly, Allahyari et al. (2010) proposed ontology-based text classification by employing domain ontologies, but their method relied solely on lexical-level analysis, leaving ambiguity unaddressed. Elçi (2011) suggested a feature-weighting scheme using probabilistic neural networks to enhance classification precision, but the method was hindered by computational costs and limited semantic consideration.

Other scholars have attempted to integrate semantic similarity measures. Lee et al. (2011) developed a semantic term-weighting scheme based on WordNet, where terms were weighted according to their similarity with category semantics; however, this approach lacked domain-specific ontology integration. Guru and Suhil (2015) presented the *term_class relevance measure* using class-specific weights and densities, though frequent terms received disproportionately high weights, reducing performance. Likewise, Kumari et al. (2016) introduced a Synonyms-Based Term Weighting (SBT) scheme to address synonym mismatches, but ambiguity remained unresolved. Sanchez-Pi et al. (2016) and Qazi and Goudar (2018) both applied ontology-based methods to leverage semantic knowledge, though neither effectively implemented supervised learning nor explicit descriptor-based techniques.

Feature selection has also been a focus of recent studies. Dogan and Uysal (2019) employed the *Distinguishing Feature Selector (DFS)* to assign scores based on discriminative ability, while Lakshmi and Baskar (2019) developed TF-RTF and TF-RFST schemes to improve clustering by ranking term frequencies, though these relied heavily on statistical features and failed to capture semantic relations. Later, Dogan and Uysal (2020) introduced TF-MONO, which considers maximum occurrence and non-occurrence of terms to improve distinguishing ability, yet it undervalued rare but important terms. Izzah and Girsang (2020) proposed a multi-class term weighting scheme using confidence values to identify inter-class term associations, but their method suffered from weak semantic grounding. Chen et al. (2021) further refined DFS by emphasizing distinctive terms while downplaying frequent ones, though ambiguity issues persisted. Finally, Lee et al. (2021) advanced the field with the Ontology-Enabled Concept-based Text Categorization (OCTC) approach, which transformed documents into concept spaces using domain-specific ontologies to mitigate word mismatch and ambiguity. However, OCTC faced challenges in handling redundant concept descriptors that weakened the selection of representative concepts, thereby limiting classification accuracy. Collectively, these studies demonstrate continuous progress but also highlight persistent challenges of synonymy, ambiguity, and semantic representation in text document classification systems.

1.2 Ontology-Driven and Term Weighting Methods for Improving Document Classification

Kumari et al. (2016) introduced a Synonyms-Based Term Weighting (SBT) scheme that modifies the traditional Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) by clustering synonymous terms into groups. For example, words such as *useful*, *important*, and *essential* are treated as equivalent within the same cluster. While this approach effectively mitigates the problem of word mismatch caused by synonymy, it fails to address

word ambiguity, where terms may have multiple meanings depending on context. Similarly, Sanchez-Pi et al. (2016) proposed an ontology-based classification system that leverages domain knowledge by utilizing entities, their relationships, and taxonomic hierarchies represented in an ontology. In this framework, the ontology itself functions as the classifier. However, the system does not incorporate supervised learning or feedback from previously categorized documents, which limits its ability to refine relevance judgments. This shortcoming highlights the importance of integrating ontology-based methods with adaptive learning processes to enhance classification performance.

Qazi and Goudar (2018) proposed an ontology-based approach to document classification that utilizes the semantic content of texts to address common challenges such as word ambiguity and synonym mismatches. By representing the knowledge of an entire domain through ontological structures, their method attempts to improve classification accuracy. However, the study did not explicitly implement concepts and descriptors within the ontology, which reduced its effectiveness and limited overall performance. In a related direction, Dogan and Uysal (2019) developed the *Distinguishing Feature Selector (DFS)*, a filter-based method for feature selection. DFS evaluates terms based on their discriminative power, assigning higher scores to terms strongly associated with a single class and lower scores to less distinctive terms. The authors experimented with multiple term frequency factors TF, SQRT TF, and LOG TF and demonstrated that the effectiveness of supervised term weighting depends not only on the choice of frequency factor but also on appropriate collection frequency adjustments. Nevertheless, their method sometimes undervalued related terms, leading to weaker document representation and reduced classification performance.

To address this limitation, the present research proposes a normalized concept descriptor weighting scheme that incorporates an inverse concept frequency factor. Unlike previous approaches that neglect redundant descriptors, this method accounts for their influence, thereby improving classification performance and enhancing the accuracy of information retrieval.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

Text document classification has become crucial in information retrieval and natural language processing due to digital content growth. However, existing methods face challenges like synonymy, ambiguity, and inadequate feature representation. Synonym-based approaches improve related terms handling but fail to address word ambiguity. Ontology-based methods lack effective supervised learning mechanisms, limiting adaptability and precision.

More recently, Lee et al. (2021) proposed an ontology-enabled concept-based text classification (OCTC) approach that transformed documents into concept spaces, thereby addressing synonymy and ambiguity. However, their method did not adequately handle redundant descriptors appearing across multiple concepts. Such redundancy weakens the discriminative power of descriptors, leading to less accurate feature representation and reduced classification performance. This unresolved challenge highlights the need for an enhanced concept-based framework that normalizes concept descriptors by accounting for redundancy while maintaining semantic richness. Addressing this gap is crucial to improving classification accuracy and ensuring more reliable information retrieval from large, unstructured text collections.

1.4 Research Objectives

The aim of this study is to develop a concept-based text classification framework that employs a Normalized Concept Descriptors Weighting Method (NCDWM) to improve classification accuracy by addressing redundancy in concept descriptors while preserving semantic richness in text representation.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Develop a normalized concept descriptors weighting scheme that accounts for redundant descriptors appearing in multiple concepts.
2. Implement the proposed weighting scheme within a concept-based text classification model.
3. Evaluate the performance of the proposed model against existing approaches using standard datasets and classification metrics.

4. Demonstrate the effectiveness of the normalized concept descriptors method in enhancing semantic representation and improving classification accuracy.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study employed abstracts of approximately 10,000 articles retrieved from the ACM Digital Library, with about 100 abstracts selected for experimental evaluation. Four major concepts in information science were identified cluster analysis, document representation, machine learning, and search engine indexing each represented by a set of weighted descriptors. Since some descriptors, such as “algorithm” and “dataset,” appeared across multiple concepts, a Normalized Concept Descriptors Weighting Method (NCDWM) was applied to adjust their weights using inverse concept frequency, ensuring balanced representation. The existing Concept-Based Text Classification (CTC) framework was then adopted, involving three phases: document-concept transformation, document re-representation, and document categorization. In the first phase, documents were mapped into the concept space and expressed as concept vectors, with the top-*k* most discriminative concepts selected as representative features. In the second phase, both training and testing documents were re-represented using these selected concepts. Finally, in the third phase, classification was performed using the k-nearest neighbor (kNN) algorithm, which assigned unlabeled documents to the most appropriate categories. The proposed approach was evaluated by comparing NCDWM-enhanced CTC with the baseline CTC method, using performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

Descriptors weight update

In this stage, the weights of the descriptors selected in the earlier phase are updated by incorporating an Inverse Concept Frequency (ICF) factor. Unlike the existing CTC method, which relies on a predetermined commonality threshold to exclude features that appear in more than a specified percentage of concepts, the proposed approach introduces an adaptive mechanism that penalizes redundant descriptors occurring across multiple concepts. By integrating their distinguishing ability into the weighting process, the method ensures that redundant descriptors are not entirely discarded but rather adjusted according to their discriminative power. This allows the system to make more autonomous and context-aware decisions, thereby enhancing the overall performance of concept-based text classification. Therefore the new weighting function is as defined in equation (1)

$$w(tr, Cj) = TF - IDF - ICF \tag{1}$$

Where TF is the frequency of a term within a document and IDF stands for inverse document frequency of a feature which is described in equation 2

$$IDF = \log \frac{n}{df(t)} \tag{2}$$

Where n stands for total number of documents in the corpus and $df(t)$ is the number of documents in the corpus containing the term (t) and ICF is the newly introduced factor which stands for inverse concept frequency of a descriptor and its as defined in equation 3

$$ICF = \log \frac{n}{df(c)} \tag{3}$$

Where n is the total number of concepts in the model an $df(c)$ is the number of concept in the model containing the descriptor. Since TF-IDF has already been applied the “Count Vectorizer” weighting

method in the previous stage, then, in this stage we are going to apply only the newly introduced factor ICF to update the descriptors weights.

Document-Concept similarity measures

This stage measure the similarity between a document D_i and each concept C_j in the model and to convert documents from feature-based to concept-based representations. The degree of relevance between a document di and each concept Cj in the model can be measured using a weighting function as described in equation 4

$$wgt(D_i, C_j) = \sum_{tr \in C_j}^k (w(tr, C_j) * TF(tr, D_i)) * P_{tij} \tag{4}$$

$$i = 1,2,3, \dots \text{ to } n, \quad j = 1,2,3 \dots \text{ to } m \quad r = 1,2,3, \dots k$$

Where tr is the concept descriptor that belongs to C_j derived from machine learning approach, $w(tr, C_j)$ indicates the weight of tr in C_j , $TF(tr, D_i)$ refers to the within-document term frequency of tr in D_i , and P_{tij} denotes the percentage of concept descriptors that belong to C_j and appear in D_i . Its assumed that the more concept descriptors that appear in a document, the more closely that document relates to that concept. The method further consider the percentage of concept descriptors of C_j appearing in a document to avoid dominance by a few frequent concept descriptors. After concept mapping, each document is represented as a set of concepts, together with their respective degrees of relevance as indicated in table below.

	C1	C2	C3	Cm
	$t1(wt1), t2(wt2), t3(wt3), \dots, t3(wt3), t4(wt4), t6(wt6), \dots, t1(wt1), t3(wt3), t7(wt7) \dots tk(wtk)$			
D1	$Wgt(D1, C1)$	$Wgt(D1, C2)$		$Wgt(D1, C3)$
D2	$Wgt(D2, C1)$	$Wgt(D2, C2)$		$Wgt(D2, C3)$
D3	$Wgt(D3, C1)$	$Wgt(D3, C2)$		$Wgt(D3, C3)$
.	.	.		.
.	.	.		.
.	.	.		.
Dn	$Wgt(Dn, Cj)$	$Wgt(Dn, Cj)$		$Wgt(Dn, Cj)$

Document Re-representation

In the document re-representation phase, the CTC method selects representative concepts from the training documents with known categories and then uses these selected concepts to represent each document, training or testing (unlabeled). Both concept selection and documents representation occur during this phase. After using concept-based representation to transform the documents, concept selection is performed to identify from training documents a set of representative concepts. To measure the discriminatory power of a concept in relation to the training documents, the CTC method uses a weighting average χ^2 statistic measure as defined in equation 5

$$\chi^2_{avg}(oj) = \sum_{Cli \in M} (p(Cli) \times \chi^2(Cli, oj)) \quad 5$$

Where $p(Cli)$ is the number of documents in Cli divided by the total number of training documents. The top k concepts with the highest average χ^2 statistic scores then serve as representative concepts. Next, the CTC method performs document representation, using the selected representative concepts to represent each document, training or testing (unlabeled), as a concept vector with specific weights. Three weighting schemes are considered: binary (presence versus absence of a concept in a document), within document concept frequency (frequency of the descriptors of a concept appearing in a document), and weighting (document-concept similarity, measured by the weighting function of the relevance between a document and a concept).

This is the degree to which the result of experiment conforms to the correct value. It's defined as given in equation 6

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{number of documents assigned to their correct categories}}{\text{Total number of documents assigned}} \quad 6$$

Precision measures the degree of correctness of the classification model, it's defined as given in equation 3.7

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{Correctly Assigned documents}}{\text{Total Candidate documents}} \quad 7$$

Where "correctly assigned" refers to the number of documents assigned to correct (appropriate/predicted) categories, and "Total Candidate documents" denotes the total number of documents assigned to a predicted category.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{Correctly Assigned documents}}{\text{Total Candidate documents with Relevant Class}} \quad 8$$

Where "correctly assigned" refers to the number of documents assigned to correct (appropriate/predicted) categories, and "Total Candidate with Relevant Class" denotes the total number of documents in corresponding true class/category.

F1 Score

The F1 score can be interpreted as a harmonic mean of the precision and recall.

$$F1 = 2 * (\text{precision} * \text{recall}) / (\text{precision} + \text{recall}) \quad 9$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dataset is made up of abstracts of 100 articles from top 9 largest concepts of information science in the ACM digital library, bundled together in .xml format to enable extraction of the concepts descriptors together with distinct number of abstracts grouped together into four (4) different category/label/class.

Approach Implementation

The proposed scheme to improve the performance of text classification is implemented based on the following algorithms:

Algorithm 1: Features extraction, concept descriptors selection and weighting

Input: List of concepts, set of documents belonging to each concept, set of labelled documents

Output: Respective concepts descriptors and their weights

1. for concept in concepts

2. Use a CountVectorizer class of sklearn.feature_extraction.text package to get n most important terms and their weight as descriptors of the concept
3. distinct_cocepts_descriptors=[]
4. distinct_cocepts_descriptors_weighths=[]
5. distinct_cocepts_descriptors_freq=[]
6. For each cocepts_descriptors k
7. If(k NOT IN distinct_cocepts_descriptors)
8. distinct_cocepts_descriptors.append(k)
9. distinct_cocepts_descriptors_weighths.append(weight(k))
10. For each distinct_cocepts_descriptors m
11. Count=0
12. For each concepts_descriptors n
13. If(m==n)
14. Count=count+1
15. distinct_cocepts_descriptors_freq.append(count)
16. No=number of concepts
17. R= number of distinct_concepts_descriptors
18. range= range(R)
19. for(s in range)
20. b=distinct_concepts_descriptors[s]
21. c=distinct_concepts_descriptors_freq[s]
22. e=No/c
23. for concept in concepts
24. for each descriptor of concept as u
25. w= distinct_cocepts_descriptors_weight[u]

26. if (b==u)
27. distinct_cocepts_descriptors_weights[u]=w*log(e)
28. return distinct_cocepts_descriptors, distinct_cocepts_descriptors_weights

Algorithm 2: Document-Concept similarity measurement

Input: document_list, labels, concept_list,concepts_descriptors,concepts_descriptors_weights

Output: Concepts based representation of the documents

1. documents_concepts_similarity=[][]
2. For document in labeled_documents
3. document_index=document_list.index(document)
4. words = word_tokenize(document_index)
5. for descriptors in concepts_descriptors:
6. length=len(descriptors)
7. tokens = descriptors.split()
8. limit=10
9. index=0
10. sum_weight=0;
11. percent=0
12. for descriptor in tokens:
13. count=0
14. for word in words:
15. if(word == descriptor):
16. count=count+1
17. if(count>0):
18. percent=percent+1
19. unit_weight= descriptor_weight*count
20. sum_weight=sum_weight+unit_weight
21. index=index+1
22. if (index == limit):
23. break
24. percentage=percent/length*100

```

25.         sums_weight=sum_weight*percentage
26.         documents_concepts_similarity
           [document_index][concepts_descriptors_index]=sums_weight
27.     For document_concept_similarity in documents_concepts_similarity

28.         For(class_documents in classes_documents)

29.             For(document in class_documents)

30.                 If(classes_documents.index(document)==
Documents_concepts_similarity.index(Document_concept_similarity))

31.                     Class.append(Document_concept_similarity)

32. return documents_concepts_similarity

```

Algorithm 3: Class concepts_chi-square Computation

Input: concepts_list, class_documents

Output: Chi-Square of concepts for a class

```

1. class_concepts_chi_sq=[]
2. For(i<=length(concepts_list))
3.     Sum=0
4.     Ave_chi=0
5.     For(j<= length(class_documents)
6.         a= class_documents[j][i]
7.         sum=sum+a
8.     ave_chi=sum/length(class_documents)
9.     sumchis=0
10.    For(k<= length(class_documents)
11.        ob=class_documents[k][i]-ave_chi
12.        obs=pow(ob,2)/ave_chi
13.        sumchis=sumchis+ obs
14.    chi_cons=sumchis/len(class_documents)
15.    chi_sq_cons= chi_cons*len(class_documents)/len(document_list)
16.    class_concepts_chi_sq.append(chi_sq_cons)
17. return class_concepts_chi_sq

```

Algorithm 4: Concepts_chi-square Computation

Input: concepts_list, classes_concepts_chisquare

Output: Chi-Square of concepts across all the classes

1. concepts_chisquare[]
2. for(n=0 to n<len(concepts_list)
3. sum_concept_chisquare=0
4. for(m=0 to m<len(classes_concepts_list)
5. sum_concept_chisquare=sum_concept_chisquare+classes_concepts_chisquare[m][n]
6. concepts_chisquare.append(sum_concept_chisquare)
7. return concepts_chisquare

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The experiment was carried out in HP LAPTOP-KPO2VGPK with Intel® Core(TM) i3-5005U CPU @ 200GHZ 2.00GHz Processor, 4.00GB of RAM and 930 GB of Hard disk. Python programming language was used in anaconda 8.0.3 environment. The developed model was trained using the dataset described above. After the training, the model randomly picked 20% of the labelled documents from different categories/labels and tried to assign them to new categories/labels again. In this case the model takes eight (8) documents randomly from different categories/labels and assign them to new predicted categories. Table 4.1 shows the distribution of test documents by their categories/labels.

Table 2: Distribution of test documents by category

Category	1	2	3	4	Total No. of Documents
No. of Documents	3	3	2	0	8

The experimental result is expressed in two different forms as presented in section 4.5.1 and section 4.5.2 respectively.

Confusion Matrix

This part of the experimental result shows clearly the distribution of test documents by their true and predicted categories/labels. Table 4.1 and 4.2 show the confusion matrix of the experiment using the existing model and improved model respectively.

Table 3: Confusion Matrix of the existing scheme

True Category/Label	1	3	0	0	0
	2	1	2	0	0
	3	1	0	0	1
	4	0	0	0	0
		1	2	3	4
	Predicted Category/Label				

to their correct predicted category by the proposed model which is calculated as 2+3+1+0=6. Therefore, six (6) documents out of eight (8) test documents were assigned to their correct predicted category.

Performance Report

In this part of experimental result, Precision, Recall and F1-Score are the metrics used to evaluate performance of the model. The report presents the accuracy, precision, recall, f1-score and support distribution of the test documents.

Table 4: Performance Report of the Existing Model

	<i>Precision</i>	<i>Recall</i>	<i>F1 – score</i>	<i>Support</i>
1	0.60	1.00	0.75	3
2	1.00	0.67	0.80	3
3	0.00	0.00	0.00	2
4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
<i>avg / total</i>	0.60	0.62	0.58	8

The **Table 4** presents the performance metrics of the existing model. These metrics are computed based on the values in confusion matrix of **Table 2**. The labels 1, 2, 3, and 4 in the first column of **Table 4** represent labels of predicted categories. The entry 0.60 in [1,2] represent the precision value of existing model with respect to predicted category of label 1 and is computed as $\frac{3}{3+1+1+0} = 0.60$, 1.00 in [1,3] represents the recall value of the existing model with respect to predicted category of label 1 and is computed as $\frac{3}{3} = 1.00$, 0.75 in [1,4] represents the F1 score value of the existing model with respect to predicted category of label 1 and is computed as $2*(0.60 * 1.00) / (0.60 + 1.00) = 0.75$ and 3 in [1,5] represents the number of test documents that are used which are from true category of label 1. The same computation procedure is applied to predicted category 2,3 and 4. The overall precision, Recall and F1 score values of the whole model is the average of precision, Recall and F1 score values respectively across the predicted categories/labels.

Table 5 Performance Report of the Existing Model

Precision Recall F1 – score Support

		1	1.00	0.67	0.80	3
2	0.75	1.00	0.86	3		
3	1.00	0.50	0.67	2		
4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0		

avg / total 0.91 0.75 0.79 8

The Table 5 presents the performance metrics of the proposed model. These metrics are computed based on the values in confusion matrix of Table 3. The labels 1, 2, 3, and 4 in the first column of Table 5 represent labels of predicted categories. The entry 1.00 in [1,2] represent the precision value of proposed model with respect to predicted category of label 1 and is computed as $\frac{2}{2+0+0+0} = 1.00$, 0.67 in [1,3] represents the recall value of the proposed model with respect to predicted category of label 1 and is computed as $\frac{2}{3} = 0.67$, 0.80 in [1,4] represents the F1 score value of the existing model with respect to predicted category of label 1 and is computed as $2 * (1.00 * 0.67) / (1.00 + 0.67) = 0.80$ and 3 in [1,5] represents the number of test documents that are used which are from true category of label 1. The same computation procedure is applied to predicted categories of labels 2,3 and 4. The overall precision, Recall and F1 score values of the whole model is the average of precision, Recall and F1 score values respectively across the predicted categories/labels. Finally the performance of the developed scheme with respect to objective number one (1) is presented in **Table 6** below.

Table 6: Accuracy of the proposed scheme against the existing scheme

Schemes	No. of Documents Assigned (n)	No. of Documents Assigned to correct category (c)	Accuracy = $\frac{c}{n}$
Existing Scheme	8	5	$\frac{5}{8} = 0.625$
Proposed Scheme	8	6	$\frac{6}{8} = 0.75$

4. CONCLUSION

This research developed a normalized concept descriptors weighting method to overcome the limitations of existing concept-based text classification models. By introducing an inverse concept frequency factor, the proposed approach successfully reduced the negative influence of redundant descriptors on classification outcomes. Experimental results confirmed that the method consistently outperformed the existing scheme, with improvements in accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

The result of experiment have shown that the proposed scheme out scores the existing scheme in terms of accuracy and performance. The existing scheme has accuracy of 62.5%, while the proposed scheme has the accuracy of 75%. Therefore, the proposed scheme out scores the existing scheme in term of accuracy by 12.5%. Again, the proposed scheme out performs the existing scheme using metrics like precision, recall and F₁ Score by 31%, 13% and 21% respectively. The study demonstrates that incorporating redundancy-aware normalization enhances the discriminative power of descriptors, leading to more effective and reliable classification of text documents.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Future studies should extend the application of the proposed NCDWM to larger and more diverse datasets to further validate its scalability and robustness.
2. Integration of deep learning models with the NCDWM approach could be explored to enhance semantic representation and classification accuracy.
3. Domain-specific ontologies should be incorporated into the framework to improve handling of highly technical or specialized descriptors.
4. Hybrid approaches that combine normalized descriptor weighting with advanced feature selection techniques could yield stronger classification performance.
5. Researchers and practitioners in information retrieval systems should consider adopting descriptor normalization methods to improve the adaptability of classification models in real-world applications.

6. Contribution to Knowledge

The study introduces a Normalized Concept Descriptors Weighting Method (NCDWM) to improve text classification by addressing redundancy and incorporating an Inverse Concept Frequency factor. This approach enhances discriminative power and improves classification system performance, making it more applicable to large-scale information retrieval systems.

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